

Composition and Stability of Indium(III)-Chrome Azurol S Chelate

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The formation of a pink-coloured chelate ($\lambda_{\max}$ 530 m μ) between indium(III) and trisodium salt of sulphodichlorohydroxydimethylfuchson dicarboxylic acid (Chrome Azurol S) has been reported. The chelate (M:Ke = 1:1) is stable between pH 3.5 and 5.5. The value of log *K* (stability constant) is 4.4 at pH 4.0 (25°). Chelation is suggested to occur between the phenolic oxygen and adjacent carboxylic oxygen.

Sulphodichlorohydroxyfuchson dicarboxylic acid (Chrome Azurol S; colour index 43825) as a suitable chromogenic reagent for metal ions has already been reported in previous publications¹⁻⁹ from these laboratories. In the present communication, the formation of a pink chelate of indium(III) and Chrome Azurol S has been reported along with the characteristics and other properties of the chelate.

EXPERIMENTAL

A weighed quantity of indium chloride (Johnson and Matthey) was dissolved in HCl(dil.), indium, estimated by the usual method, and the solution suitably diluted. An aqueous stock solution of Chrome Azurol S (trisodium salt; B.D.H. indicator) was prepared.

A Unicam SP 500 spectrophotometer with 1 cm glass cells was used for absorbance measurements; L and N pH-meter for pH measurements and LKB electrophoresis equipment for determination of the charge on the chelate were used.

All measurements were made in an air-conditioned room, maintained at 25° ± 1°. pH of the solutions and mixtures was adjusted to 4.0 ± 0.2.

In view of the observations of Srivastava *et al.*¹⁰ that Chrome Azurol S behaved as a colloidal electrolyte, dilute solutions of the order of 10⁻⁴M were employed in the absorptometric measurements.

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Nature of the Complexes Formed.—Absorbance measurements of the mixtures containing 1:0.5, 1:1, 1:2, 1:3, and 1:4 of indium:CAS showed that the $\lambda_{\max}$ of the complex formed was at 530 m μ in all the cases at pH 4.0. The reagent has $\lambda_{\max}$ at 490 m μ at the same pH. Thus the formation of only one complex may reasonably be assumed under the conditions.

Composition of the Chelate.—The composition of the chelate was studied by absorbance measurements using (i) the method of continued variations, (ii) the mole-ratio method, and (iii) the slope-ratio method. The results obtained by (i), recorded in Table I, as well as by the other two methods indicate a 1:1 composition for the chelate (c = concentration of metal ion; c' = concentration of the reagent; $p = c'/c$).

FIG. 1. Composition by the method of continued variations at 580 m μ ($p=1$; pH 4.0).

Curve A: $c = 2.00 \times 10^{-4}M$

Curve B: $c = 1.33 \times 10^{-4}M$

Curve C: $c = 1.00 \times 10^{-4}M$

TABLE I

Composition of indium-CAS chelate by the method of continued variations.

Total volume = 25ml. $p = 1$. pH = 4.0.

Figure.	Curves.	$c \times 10^4$.	Wave length.	Volume of $InCl_3$ at peak.	Composition. ($In^{3+} : CAS$).
1	A	2.00M	580m μ	12.50 ml	1 : 1
	B	1.33	580	12.50	1 : 1
	C	1.00	580	12.50	1 : 1
Figure not shown	A	2.00	590	12.50	1 : 1
	B	1.33	590	12.50	1 : 1
	C	1.00	590	12.50	1 : 1

Influence of Hydrogen-ion Concentration.—Mixtures containing $8.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ indium chloride and CAS in the ratio of 1:1 at different pH values were prepared, their absorbances measured at various wave lengths, and the results plotted graphically. It is indicated that $\lambda_{\max}$ of the chelate (530 m μ) holds good from pH 3.5 to 5.5, which shows that the chelate is stable within this range of pH.

Evaluation of the Stability Constant.—The values of $\log K$ (pH 4.0), as determined by two different methods, are shown in Table II.

TABLE II

Stability constant and change in free energy formation of the chelate.*

Method.	pH.	Log K .	ΔG° at 25°(kcal.).
Mukherjee and Dey ¹¹	4.0	4.4 ± 0.1	-6.10 ± 0.15
Mole-ratio method	4.0	4.8 ± 0.1	-6.60 ± 0.15

* $\Delta G^\circ = -RT \ln K$.

Suggestions on the Structure of the Chelate.—On mixing solutions of indium and CAS, both brought to pH 4.0, the pH dropped to 3.7, showing the liberation of hydrogen ions as a result of chelation. Thus it is likely that chelation takes place between the hydroxyl oxygen and the adjacent carboxylic oxygen, giving rise to an anionic complex, as has been confirmed by the complete adsorption of the colour by ion-exchange resin, Amberlite IR-45 (OH) (B.D. H. AnalaR) and further by electrophoretic experiments.

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